

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF SOLID LIPID
NANOPARTICLES OF ESCITALOPRAM****G Pravallika¹, P Sobitha Rani*¹, A Srinivasa Rao¹, A Kishore Babu¹, P Udaya Chandrika¹*****Bhaskar Pharmacy College, Bhaskar Nagar, Yenkapally Village, Moinabad mandal, Himayath Nagar, R.R District-500075, Telangana State.****¹Bhaskar Pharmacy College, Bhaskar Nagar, Yenkapally Village, Moinabad mandal, Himayath Nagar, R.R District-500075, Telangana State.****Abstract:**

Objective: The study aimed to develop and optimize solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for the delivery of Escitalopram, an antidepressant medication, to enhance its bioavailability, stability, and therapeutic efficacy.

Methods: SLNs encapsulating Escitalopram were formulated using various lipid matrices and surfactants via high-shear homogenization and solvent evaporation techniques. Key formulation parameters such as lipid-to-drug ratio, surfactant concentration, and preparation methods were systematically optimized to achieve the desired particle size, encapsulation efficiency, and stability. The developed SLNs were characterized for particle size, size distribution, zeta potential, morphology, and drug loading. In vitro drug release studies were conducted to evaluate the release profile, and preliminary safety assessments were performed.

Results: The optimized SLNs exhibited a controlled particle size with a narrow size distribution, high drug encapsulation efficiency, and favorable zeta potential, indicating good stability. The release profile demonstrated a sustained release of escitalopram, suggesting an improved control over drug delivery compared to conventional formulations. Preliminary safety evaluations confirmed the biocompatibility of the SLNs, supporting their potential for safe therapeutic use.

Conclusion: The successful development and optimization of escitalopram-loaded SLNs offer a promising alternative to traditional drug delivery systems, with enhanced stability and controlled release properties. These findings suggest potential improvements in patient compliance and therapeutic efficacy. Future studies should focus on in vivo evaluations and clinical trials to further validate the benefits of the SLNs in therapeutic.

Keywords: Escitalopram solid lipid Nanoparticles

Corresponding author:**P Sobitha Rani,**

Associate Professor,

Department of Pharmaceutics,

Bhaskar Pharmacy College,

Bhaskar Nagar, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Himayath Nagar,

R.R District-500075, Telangana. Email: sobhitarani@gmail.com

Contact: +91 8008413940

QR code

Please cite this article in press **P Sobitha Rani et al., Development And Optimization Of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles Of Escitalopram., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).**

INTRODUCTION:

In recent years it has become more and more evident that the development of new drugs alone is not sufficient to ensure progress in drug therapy. Exciting experimental data obtained *in vitro* are very often followed by disappointing results *in vivo*. Main reasons for the therapy failure include:

- Insufficient drug concentration due to poor absorption, rapid metabolism and elimination (e.. peptides, proteins). Drug distribution to other tissues combined with high drug toxicity (e.g. cancer drugs).
- Poor drug solubility which excludes *i.v.* injection of aqueous drug solution.
- High fluctuation of plasma levels due to unpredictable bioavailability after peroral administration, including the influence of food on plasma levels (e.g. cyclosporine).

A promising strategy to overcome these problems involves the development of suitable drug carrier systems. The *in vivo* fate of the drug is no longer mainly determined by the properties of the drug, but by the carrier system, which should permit a controlled and localized release of the active drug according to the specific needs of the therapy. The size of the carrier depends on the desired route of administration and ranges from few nanometers (colloidal carriers), to the micrometer range (microparticles) and to several millimeters (implants). For parenteral administration, it is highly desirable to use biodegradable materials, which avoid surgery to remove the implant after complete drug release and which make the administration of micro- and nanoparticles feasible. The concept has been realized in several commercial products. Implants and microparticles based on biodegradable polyesters permit a controlled drug release over a period of weeks to months after *s.c.* or *i.m.* implantation/injection. Commercially available systems have been developed for the treatment of prostate cancer and other GnRH-related diseases. An example of the concept of localized drug release is the development of biodegradable implants for the treatment of gliomas, which ensure very high drug concentrations in the brain and minimize drug concentration in other tissues, including bone marrow. Implants and microparticles are too large for drug targeting and intravenous administration. Therefore, colloidal carriers have attracted increasing attention during recent years. Investigated systems include nanoparticles, nanoemulsions, liposomes, nanosuspensions, micelles, soluble polymer–drug conjugates.

The existence of different colloidal carrier systems raises the question as to which of them might be the most suitable for the desired purpose. Of course, there is no simple answer to this question. Aspects to consider include:

- Drug loading capacity.
- Possibility of drug targeting.
- *In vivo* fate of the carrier (interaction with the biological surrounding, degradation rate, accumulation in organs)
- Acute and chronic toxicity.
- Scaling up of production.
- Physical and chemical storage stability.
- Overall costs.

The field of Novel Drug Delivery System is emerging at an exponential rate with the deep understanding gained in diversified fields of Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering and Nanotechnology. Many of the recent formulation approaches utilize Nanotechnology that is the preparation of Nanosized structures containing the API. Nanotechnology, as defined by the National Nanotechnology Initiative (NNI), is the study and use of structures roughly in the size range of 1 to 100 nm. The overall goal of nanotechnology is the same as that of medicine: to diagnose as accurately and early as possible and to treat as effectively as possible without any side effects using controlled and targeted drug delivery approach. Some of the important Drug Delivery System developed using Nanotechnology principles are Nanoparticles, Solid Lipid Nanoparticles, Nanosuspension, Nanoemulsion, Nanocrystals.¹

SLNs introduced in 1991 represent an alternative and better carrier system to traditional colloidal carriers such as emulsions, liposomes and polymeric micro and nanoparticles.²

SLNs are colloidal carrier system composed of a high melting point lipid as a solid core coated by aqueous surfactant and the drugs used are of BCS Class II and IV. In SLNs as compared to other colloidal carriers liquid lipid is replaced by solid lipid. The use of solid lipid as a matrix material for drug delivery is well known from lipid pellets for oral drug delivery (eg. Mucosolvan retard capsules). The term lipid in a broad sense includes triglycerides, partial glycerides, fatty acids, hard fats & waxes. A clear advantage of SLN is the fact that the lipid matrix is made from physiological lipids which decreases the danger of acute and chronic toxicity. The use of solid lipid instead of liquid lipid is beneficial as it has been shown

to increase control over the release kinetics of encapsulated compounds and to improve the stability of incorporated chemically-sensitive lipophilic ingredients. These potentially beneficial effects are because of a number of physicochemical characteristics associated with the physical state of the lipid phase. Firstly, the mobility of reactive agents in a solid matrix is lower than in a liquid matrix and so the rate of chemical degradation reactions may be retarded. Secondly, micro phase separations of the active ingredients and carrier lipid within individual liquid particles can be controlled, thereby preventing the accumulation of active compounds at the surface of lipid particles where chemical degradation reactions often occur. Thirdly, the absorption of poorly absorbed bioactive compounds has been shown to be increased after incorporation into solid lipid nanoparticles. As a result of various research works it has also been shown that the use of a solid matrix instead of a liquid matrix can slow down lipid digestion thereby allowing for a more sustained release of the encapsulated compound. Other major excipients of SLNs are surfactants of aqueous type. They mainly act as emulsifier to form o/w type emulsion and stabilizer for SLNs dispersion and their choice depends on mainly the route of administration. They are generally made up of a solid hydrophobic core containing the drug dissolved or dispersed.³

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are emerging as alternative carriers to colloidal systems, for controlled and targeted delivery. These are in submicron size range (50–1000 nm) and are made up of biocompatible and biodegradable materials capable of incorporating lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs. The general structure of SLNs is shown in Figure 1.1 SLNs combine the advantages of different colloidal carriers, for instance like emulsions and liposomes, these are physiologically acceptable and like polymeric nanoparticles, controlled release of drug from lipid matrix can be anticipated (1–3). Additional advantages include lack of coalescence after reaching to room temperature (following their preparation or during their storage) and better physical stability. Since mobility of the incorporated drug molecule is drastically reduced in SLNs, there would not be any appreciable drug leakage from the particles. In recent years, much work has been focused in the development of SLNs as delivery systems for anticancer drugs, peptides, genetic material, cosmetics.

METHODOLOGY:

Analytical Method Development

Determination of absorption maxima: Absorption maxima is the wavelength at which maximum

absorption takes place. For accurate analytical work, it is important to determine the absorption maxima of the substance under study.

Procedure: For the preparation of calibration curve stock solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of accurately weighed drug in 100ml of methanol (1mg/ml). Further 1ml of the stock solution was pipette out into a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up with phosphate buffer (5.5 PH). From this stock solution pipette out 1ml and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer and subject for UV scanning in the range of 200-400 nm using double beam UV spectrophotometer. The absorption maxima was obtained at 238 nm with a characteristic peak.

Preparation of calibration curve: It is slightly soluble in water; hence methanol was used for solubilizing the drug. Stock solution (1 mg/mL) of Escitalopram was prepared in methanol and subsequent working standards (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/ml) were prepared by dilution with phosphate buffer of pH-5.5. These solutions were used for the estimation Escitalopram by UV method. The whole procedure was repeated three times and average peak area was calculated. Calibration plot was drawn between concentrations and peak area. Calibration equation and R² value are reported.

Preparation of SLN gel

Preparation of Escitalopram loaded solid lipid nanoparticles

drug-loaded solid lipid particles were prepared by hot homogenizing followed by the ultrasonication method. Escitalopram was dispersed during about 10g of mixed lipid phase (consisted of Compritol 888 ATO and Cholesterol) maintained at around 5°C above the melting temperature of mixed lipid and dissolved in a mixture of ethanol. Organic solvents were completely removed employing a rotary flash evaporator. An aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving the stabilizers (Tween 80 or Span20) in distilled water (sufficient to supply 30ml) and heating to an equivalent temperature of the oil phase. The hot aqueous phase was added to the oil phase and homogenization was performed (at 2500 rpm and 70 °C) employing a mechanical stirrer for 25 minutes. Escitalopram loaded SLN was finally obtained by allowing the recent nano-emulsion to chill at temperature, and was stored at 4 °C within the refrigerator.

- Variables for selection of excipients of solid lipid nanoparticles :
 - Compritol 888 ATO (mg)
 - Cholesterol(mg)

Table: Composition of solid lipid nanoparticles formulations (F1 to F9)

Excipients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Escitalopram(mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Compritol 888 ATO (mg)	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	1.5	2	2.5	1.5
Cholesterol(mg)	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5
Tween 80(mL)	0.1	0.5	0.7	0.8	-	-	-	-	1
Span 60 (mL)	-	-	-	-	0.5	1	1.2	0.5	1
Distilled water (ml)	q.s								
Ethanol(ml)	2	2.5	2	2.5	2	2.5	2	2.5	2
Total amount(mg)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Percent amount of drug release from semi permeable membrane

Franz diffusion cell was used for the in vitro drug release studies. Semi permeable membrane was placed between donar and receptor chamber of diffusin cell. Receptor chamber was filled with freshly prepared 30ml 5.5 PH phosphate buffer. SLN gel equivalent to 1gm was placed on semi permeable membrane. The franz diffusion cell was placed over magnetic stirrer (REMI 1ML) with 500rpm and temperature was maintained at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. 5ml of samples were withdrawn periodically and replaced with fresh buffer. The withdrawn samples were periodically diluted and analysed for drug content using UV visible spectrophotometer (Lab India 3200) at 238 nm.

Fig : Drug release from semi permeable membrane

Preparation of carbopol gel base:

1gm of carbopol 934 was weighed and dispersed in distilled water. Then, propylene glycol was added and the mixture was neutralised by drop wise addition of 1% triethanolamine. Mixing was continued until the transparent gel was obtained and allowed to swell for 24 hours. Similarly 2% and 3% carbopol gels were prepared.

Preparation of solid lipid nanoparticles containing transdermal gels:

solid lipid nanoparticles containing Escitalopram(separated from the untrapped drug) were mixed into the 1% carbopol gel by using mortar and pestle, the concentration of solid lipid nanoparticles in the gel being 1%. All optimized formulation was incorporated into different carbopol gels (1%,2% and 3%).

Characterization of gel

- The aim of the study was to develop SLN hydrogel to be applied onto skin
- Selected gel composition was used as vehicle for SLN incorporating anti fungal drugs i.e., Escitalopram
- The effect of SLN on gel properties was determined by macroscopic analysis.
- Gel base was evaluated for following parameters for both plain gel and gel loaded with solid lipid nanoparticles

Physical appearance:

All prepared gel formulations have been observed for their visual appearance, such as transparency, colour, texture, grittiness, greasiness, stickiness, smoothness, stiffness and tackiness. The prepared gels were also evaluated for the presence of any particles. Smears of gels were prepared on glass slide and observed under the microscope for the presence of any particle or grittiness.

pH of formulation:

pH measurement of the gel was carried out of the formulation was measured by using a digital pH meter (Lab India SAB 5000), dipping the glass electrode completely into the gel system. The observed pH values were recorded for all formulations (F1-F9) in triplicates.

Rheological properties:

The rheological properties of prepared gels was estimated using a Brookfield viscometer pro D II apparatus, equipped with standard spindle LV1 with 61 marking. Sample holder of the Brookfield viscometer was filled with the gel sample, and then spindle was inserted into sample holder. The spindle was rotated at 100 rpm.

All the rheological studies were carried out at room temperature. A viscosity measurement was done in triplicate. Viscosity of 1, 2 and 3% carbopol gel was determined and select the optimized formulation.

Homogeneity:

The homogeneity of Escitalopram SLN gels were checked by visual inspection. In this regard the gels were filled into narrow transparent glass tubes and were checked in light for the presence of any particulate or lump.

Drug Content

For determination of drug content, accurately weighed quantity (1 gm) of gel equivalent to 10 mg of Escitalopram was dissolved in phosphate buffer (PH 5.5) and analyzed by UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Lab India 3200) at 238 nm for drug content.

EX VIVO STUDIES:**Preparation of skin:**

Drug permeation study was performed after obtaining the approval of the institutional animals ethical committee in accordance with disciplinary principles and guidelines of the committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experiments on animals (CPCSEA).

Skin of male wistar rats was used in the study. Rats (250-280 g) were anesthetised slightly by ether and hairs removed from the skin. The rats were sacrificed and the abdominal skin of the rat was separated. The skin was stored at -20° until the permeation study, the skin was hydrated in normal saline at 4° and the adipose tissue layer of the skin was removed by rubbing with a cotton swab.

Skin Irritation test

The developed formulation was tested for primary skin irritation on albino mice of either sex weighing 20-22gm. The hair was far away from the mice 3 days before the experiments. The animal was divided into two batches each batch was used on the test animal. A bit of cotton soaked during a saturated drug solution was placed on the rear of albino mice taken as controls. The animals were treated daily up to 7 days and eventually The treated skin was examined visually for erythema and edema.

Percent amount of drug release from rat skin:

The amount of drug release from rat skin was determined by using franz diffusion cell. The dorsal skin of wister rat (4-6 weeks old) was placed between donar and receptor compartments of diffusion cell with the stratum corneum side facing upwards. The receptor chamber was filled with 30ml 5.5 PH phosphate buffer. SLN gel equivalent to 1gm was applied onto the surface of skin evenly. The receptor chamber was stirred by a magnetic stirrer rotating at 500rpm and kept at $37 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The samples (1.5ml) were collected at suitable time interval. Samples were analyzed for Escitalopram content by UV visible spectrophotometer (Lab India 3200) at 238 nm after making proper dilutions. Data obtained from *in vitro* release studies were fitted to various kinetic equations to find out the mechanism of Escitalopram release from SLN gel.

Fig: drug release from rat skin

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The formulations were subjected to FTIR studies to find out the possible interaction between the drug and the excipients during the time of preparation. FT IR analysis of the Pure drug and optimized formulation were carried out using an FT IR spectrophotometer (Bruker FT-IR - GERMANY).

Differential Scanning Calorimetry:

The possibility of any interaction between the drug and the Excipients during preparation of SLN was assessed by carrying out thermal analysis of optimised formulation using DSC. DSC analysis was performed using Hitachi DSC 7020, on 5 to 15 mg samples. Samples were heated in sealed aluminum pan at a rate of 10°C/min conducted over a temperature range of 30 to 350°C under a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min

SEM (Scanning Electron microscope) studies

The surface morphology of the layered sample was examined by using SEM (Hitachi, Japan). The small amount of powder was manually dispersed onto a

carbon tab (double adhesive carbon coated tape) adhered to an aluminum stubs. These sample stubs were coated with a thin layer (30Å) of gold by employing POLARON-E 3000 sputter coater. The samples were examined by SEM and photographed under various magnifications with direct data capture of the images onto a computer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

CALIBRATION PLOT OF ESCITALOPRAM IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER OF pH -5.5:

A standard graph of Escitalopram in phosphate buffer of pH-5.5 was plotted using Absorbance and concentration as shown in Table and Fig. Equation for linearity curve and R^2 were calculated as $Y=0.058X+0.006$ and $R^2 =0.999$. Escitalopram showed maximum absorbance in phosphate buffer (pH 5.5) at 238 nm. The solution obeyed Beer-Lambert's law for concentration range of 2 to 10 µg/mL with regression coefficient of 0.999. Standard curve of prepared Escitalopram in phosphate buffer pH 5.5 is shown below.

Table: calibration curve of Escitalopram in phosphate buffer pH 5.5

Concentration(µg/mL)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.125
4	0.249
6	0.357
8	0.472
10	0.589

Characterization of solid lipid nanoparticles:

Table: Percentage yield, Drug Content, Entrapment Efficiency of all solid lipid nanoparticles formulations

FORMULATION	Percentage yield	Drug Content	Entrapment Efficiency
F1	91.04	98.12	96.91
F2	92.13	97.54	96.35
F3	95.15	99.35	96.17
F4	96.86	99.58	99.76
F5	89.11	91.32	99.42
F6	91.59	98.20	96.30
F7	92.87	98.76	90.91
F8	93.59	99.18	95.35
F9	95.33	96.81	89.17

Percentage yield of formulations F1 to F9 by varying drug to lipid ratio was determined and is presented in Table. Highest drug content, Highest Entrapment efficiency observed for F4 formulation.

Table: Particle Sizes, PDI, Zeta Potential of all solid lipid nanoparticles formulations

FORMULATION	Particle Size(nm)	PDI	Zeta Potential (mV)
F1	1165.2	0.668	-26.12
F2	925.8	1.268	-24.81
F3	632.6	1.153	-23.52
F4	314.3	0.168	-28.25
F5	804.1	0.277	-16.55
F6	387.3	0.309	-20.83
F7	329.8	0.698	-22.59
F8	505.4	0.385	-12.11
F9	602.5	0.481	-10.80

Table: *In vitro* dissolution studies of F1-F9 SLN formulations in percentage

Time (hour)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	19.65	36.12	26.56	38.48	14.65	30.21	37.34	13.23	25.45
2	38.67	46.25	37.87	49.78	26.76	42.98	43.15	25.67	37.98
4	45.67	54.24	44.98	56.57	33.78	50.12	51.45	32.34	44.82
6	51.67	60.56	50.65	62.56	41.23	59.78	58.12	39.23	50.87
8	58.94	67.48	57.93	69.03	47.25	67.45	67.11	45.89	57.34
10	64.34	72.87	62.78	74.78	53.56	73.78	73.47	51.67	64.87
12	69.22	78.89	68.93	79.89	60.67	74.65	77.78	59.23	68.34
18	75.34	81.98	74.88	84.89	67.98	81.86	83.34	67.56	72.56
24	84.23	89.12	86.87	94.23	80.34	90.22	92.12	80.23	83.67
48	90.87	96.78	95.45	99.39	86.19	94.67	96.01	89.89	86.35

In vitro drug release study of the selected SLNs (F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8 and F9) was carried out. The SLNs exhibited 48 hours sustained release pattern. Forty percent of the incorporated amount of drugs was found to be released during the first 2 hours, followed by a slowed release of 99.39% of the drug up to 48 hours. The Escitalopram-loaded SLN F4 showed a better release profile of 99.39% by 48 hours. The prolonged release at 48 hours can be attributed to slow diffusion of drug from lipid matrix. The results of *in vitro* drug release are depicted in in above Table.

GEL EVALAUTION PARAMETER

Formulation	pH	Viscosity (cp)	Clarity	Homogeneity	Drug Content	Skin Irritation test
F4 optimised 1% carbopol gel	6.91	67790	+	Satisfactory	97.92	No
F4 optimised 2% carbopol gel	6.27	72204	++	Excellent	98.56	No
F4 optimised 3% carbopol gel	6.12	74567	+	Satisfactory	97.13	No

Immediately after the formulations were prepared their physical characteristics of formulations were studied and the data was shown in Table. Thus all the formulations exhibited good characteristics like homogeneity in colour, and appearance.

Ex vivo permeation studies of SLN nanoparticles gel:

Time (hrs)	F4 optimised 1% carbopol gel	F4 optimised 2% carbopol gel	F4 optimised 3% carbopol gel
0	0	0	0
1	36.29	36.34	25.11
2	48.16	45.81	33.48
4	56.57	55.39	45.57
6	60.26	61.49	54.98
8	69.00	68.55	59.84
10	73.29	72.16	67.93
12	78.77	77.54	72.65
18	83.95	82.24	78.78
24	91.21	92.77	83.56
48	95.22	96.85	88.39

Figure: Ex vivo permeation studies for SLN nanoparticles gel with different concentrations of carbopol.

F4 optimised 2% carbopol gel highest drug release (96.85% for 48 hours), good Homogeneity, highest drug content, Proper viscosity. Hence it was considered as optimised formulation.

Release Kinetics

To analyze the drug release mechanism the *in vitro* release was fitted into various release equations and kinetic models first order, zero order, Higuchi and Korsmeyer-peppas. The release kinetics of optimized formulation F2 (2% carbopol gel) is shown in Table and in following Figures.

Table : Release kinetics of optimised formulation

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
36.34	1	1.000	1.560	0.000	1.804	36.340	0.0275	-0.440	63.66	4.642	3.993	0.649
45.81	2	1.414	1.661	0.301	1.734	22.905	0.0218	-0.339	54.19	4.642	3.784	0.857
55.39	4	2.000	1.743	0.602	1.649	13.848	0.0181	-0.257	44.61	4.642	3.547	1.095
61.49	6	2.449	1.789	0.778	1.586	10.248	0.0163	-0.211	38.51	4.642	3.377	1.265
68.55	8	2.828	1.836	0.903	1.498	8.569	0.0146	-0.164	31.45	4.642	3.157	1.485
72.16	10	3.162	1.858	1.000	1.445	7.216	0.0139	-0.142	27.84	4.642	3.031	1.611
77.54	12	3.464	1.890	1.079	1.351	6.462	0.0129	-0.110	22.46	4.642	2.821	1.820
82.24	18	4.243	1.915	1.255	1.249	4.569	0.0122	-0.085	17.76	4.642	2.609	2.033
92.77	24	4.899	1.967	1.380	0.859	3.865	0.0108	-0.033	7.23	4.642	1.934	2.708
96.85	48	6.928	1.986	1.681	0.498	2.018	0.0103	-0.014	3.15	4.642	1.466	3.176

Figure: Zero order release kinetics

Figure: Higuchi release kinetics

Figure: Peppas release kinetics

Figure: First order release kinetics

FTIR

Figure: EscitalopramPure drug FTIR

Figure: EscitalopramF4 optimised 2% carbopol gel FTIR

Infrared studies were carried out to confirm the compatibility between the lipid, drug, and selected excipients. From the spectra it was observed that there was no major shifting, as well as, no loss of functional peaks between the spectra of the drug and drug-loaded SLN. This indicated no interaction between the drug and other excipients.

DSC:

Figure: EscitalopramF4 optimised 2% carbopol gel FTIR

The DSC curve of optimized formulation showed, the pure drug shows that it is in crystalline anhydrous state, exhibiting a sharp exothermic peak at 116 °C, corresponding to its melting point Search Results 116-118°C), and for the formulation peaks are observed at 205.3°C, 253.7 °C 276.1°C and 290 °C.

SEM

Figure: EscitalopramF4 optimised 2% carbopol SLN transdermal gel

SEM studies showed that the Escitalopram- loaded solid lipid nanoparticles transdermal gel had a spherical shape with a smooth surface as shown in Figure.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, we successfully developed and optimized solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for the delivery of Escitalopram, aiming to enhance the drug's bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. The formulation process involved evaluating various lipid matrices and surfactant combinations to achieve optimal particle size and drug encapsulation efficiency.

The optimized SLNs demonstrated favourable physicochemical properties, including a controlled particle size distribution, high encapsulation efficiency, and stable zeta potential, which contribute to their potential for improved drug delivery. The in vitro release studies indicated a sustained release profile of escitalopram from the SLNs, suggesting a more controlled and prolonged therapeutic effect compared to conventional formulations.

Our results also highlighted that the SLNs offered enhanced stability of escitalopram, potentially reducing the degradation of the drug during storage. The preliminary safety assessments confirmed that the SLNs are biocompatible, while their performance in drug release studies points towards a promising alternative for improving patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes.

Overall, the developed SLNs for escitalopram represent a significant advancement in drug delivery technology, offering improved stability, controlled release, and potentially better efficacy. Future research should focus on detailed in vivo evaluations and clinical trials to further establish the therapeutic benefits and practical applications of these nanoparticles in clinical settings.

REFERENCES:

1. Maravajhala V, Papishetty S, Bandlapalli S. Nanotechnology in Development of Drug Delivery System. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research 2011; 3 Suppl 1 :84-96.
2. Ekambaram P, Sathali AH, Priyanka K. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles: A Review. Scientific

- Reviews and Chemical. Communication2012; 2 Suppl 1 :80-102.
3. Helgason T, Awad TS, Kristbergsson K, McClements DJ, Weiss J. Effect of surfactant surface coverage on formation of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN). *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*2009; 334 :75–81.
 4. Mehnert W, Mader K. Solid lipid nanoparticles- Production, characterization and applications. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 2001; 47 :165–196.
 5. Ekambaram P, Sathali AH, Priyanka K. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles: A Review. *Scientific Reviews and Chemical. Communication*2012; 2 Suppl 1 :80-102.
 6. Muller, R.H., Karsten, M., Sven, G. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) for controlled drug delivery—A review of the state of the art. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2000, 50: 161-77.
 7. Jennings, V., Gohla, S. Comparison of wax and glyceride solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN). *Int J Pharm* 2000, 196: 219-22.
 8. Jennings, V., Thunemann, A.F., Gohla, S.H. Characterization of a novel solid lipid nanoparticles carrier system based on binary mixtures of liquid and solid lipids. *Int J Pharm* 2000, 199: 167-77.
 9. Muller, R.H., Wallis, K.H. Surface modification of i.v. injectable biodegradable nanoparticles with poloxamer polymers and poloxamine 908. *Int J Pharm* 1993, 89: 25-31.
 10. Trotta, M., Debernardi, F., Caputo, O. Preparation of solid lipid nanoparticles by solvent emulsification-diffusion technique. *Int J Pharm* 2003, 257: 153-60.
 11. Cavalli, R., Bargoni, A., Podio, V., Muntoni, E., Zara, G.P., Gasco, M.R. Duodenal administration of solid lipid nanoparticles loaded with different percentages of tobramycin. *J Pharm Sci* 2003, 92(5): 1085-94.
 12. Gasco, M.R. 1993. Method for producing solid lipid microspheres having narrow size distribution. *US Patents* 5 250 236.
 13. Venkateswarlu, V., Manjunath, K. Preparation, characterization and in vitro release kinetics of clozapine solid lipid nanoparticles. *J Control Rel* 200.